

INDUSAC Platform Final Version

DELIVERABLE
D2.7

Version 1
08 2025

Project Number: 101070297

Project Acronym: INDUSAC

Project title: Quick Challenge-driven, Human-centred Co-Creation Mechanism for INDUSty-Academia Collaborations

Starting date: 01/09/2022

Duration in months: 36

Call (part) identifier: HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01

Topic: HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01-20

Technical reference

<i>Deliverable:</i>	
<i>Work Package:</i>	2
<i>Due Date:</i>	M36
<i>Submission Date:</i>	19/08/2025
<i>Start Date of Project:</i>	01/09/2022
<i>Duration of Project:</i>	36 months
<i>Organisation Responsible for Deliverable:</i>	Innoget
<i>Version:</i>	1
<i>Status:</i>	Final
<i>Author name(s):</i>	Elene Bokeria, Jordi Rafols, Raph Castro
<i>Reviewer(s):</i>	INDUSAC partners and the INDUSAC Steering Committee
<i>Type:</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Report <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other
<i>Dissemination level:</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU <input type="checkbox"/> SEN

History of Changes:

Date	Comments	Version
08 July 2025	<i>initial draft by partners responsible</i>	V0.1
16 July 2025	<i>draft based on feedback from project partners</i>	V0.2
4 August 2025	<i>draft based on feedback from Steering Committee</i>	V0.3
19 August 2025	<i>final version submitted to Participant Portal</i>	V1.0

SUMMARY OF THE PROJECT

INDUSAC's main objective is to develop and validate a state-of-the-art, Industry-Academia collaboration (IAC) mechanism for quick, challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation. It aims to build upon pre-existing IAC mechanisms such as EIT KICs and to facilitate a simple, user-friendly co-creation process that allows to develop solutions that clearly address the needs and interests of companies, students, and researchers in the EU, with special attention to widening and associated countries. Of a highly digitalised nature, our project pilots the mechanism's two main components: a methodology developed by applying human-centred design principles and an online platform aimed at connecting stakeholders from the industry-academia ecosystem and at supporting them throughout their co-creation journey.

The INDUSAC methodology provides the guidance and tools needed to power the process, whilst the platform stands as a networking space for stakeholders to connect, as well as a co-creation arena to develop joint solutions. Through the experience of supporting transnational co-creation teams throughout the project lifetime, the INDUSAC mechanism and its two key components were successively improved until the project ends, delivering a tested mechanism ready for replication and upskilling. INDUSAC created a dynamic community of industry-academia stakeholders, including companies, students and researchers. The INDUSAC achieved a strong interdisciplinary, cross-sectorial and geographically balanced partnership that leveraged the needed expertise and network to achieve our project's goals.

ABSTRACT

This deliverable outlines the final version of the INDUSAC platform (<https://indusac.innogetcloud.com/>), the digital foundation of the INDUSAC mechanism for fostering quick, challenge-driven and human-centred co-creation between industry, academia and students. As a core output of Work Package 2 (WP2), the platform has been conceptualised, designed, developed, and incrementally improved based on user feedback, performance metrics, and piloting outcomes. The INDUSAC platform serves a dual purpose: it is both a **matchmaking hub** for students, researchers, and companies to form co-creation teams, and a **project management environment** enabling the execution of these collaborations in a seamless and transparent way. This final version integrates iterative improvements derived from piloting activities and stakeholder engagement. It supports all phases of the co-creation lifecycle, including onboarding, challenge submission, team formation, project collaboration, financial support management and reporting. The INDUSAC platform stands ready for post-project replication, integration with broader innovation ecosystems, and scaling within EU initiatives focused on industry-academia collaboration, student upskilling and innovation capacity building.

LIST OF ACRONYMS

API	Application Programing Interface
E2E testing	End-to-End testing
INDUSAC	Quick challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation mechanism for INDUSty-Academia-Collaborations
KIT	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience
WP	Work Package

TABLE OF CONTENTS

SUMMARY OF THE PROJECT	3
ABSTRACT	4
LIST OF ACRONYMS	5
I. INTRODUCTION	7
II. DEVELOPMENT ROADMAP	8
2.1 Initial Requirements and Architecture	8
2.2 Beta Version and Pre-Validation	8
2.3 Full Launch and Iterative Improvement	9
III. PLATFORM FINAL FEATURES	10
3.1 User Registration and Onboarding	10
3.2 Challenge Submission and Management (for Companies)	11
3.3 Matchmaking and Motivation Letter Workflow	11
3.4 Project Collaboration and Management	11
3.5 Support Features and Resources	12
3.6 Analytics and Reporting	12
IV. PLATFORM PERFORMANCE METRICS	13
4.1 Technical Performance	13
4.2 Community Engagement and Reach	13
V. COMPLIANCE AND LEGAL CONSIDERATIONS	15
5.1 Data Protection (GDPR Compliance)	15
5.2 Intellectual Property (IP) Rights	15
VI. CONCLUSION	16
I. LIST OF FIGURES	17
II. LIST OF TABLES	19

I. INTRODUCTION

The INDUSAC project addresses the critical need to bridge the gap between academic knowledge and industrial innovation by enabling rapid, challenge-oriented collaboration between students, researchers and companies across the Europe. To facilitate this mechanism, the INDUSAC platform (<https://indusac.innogetcloud.com/>) was developed as a central digital infrastructure, delivering an efficient, user-friendly environment for co-creation.

Work Package 2 (WP2), led by INNOGET, was responsible for designing, developing, launching and maintaining this platform. The platform's development was closely coordinated with WP1 (Methodology), ensuring that the user journey and functional design reflected human-centred design principles and practical co-creation workflows.

From the platform's technical foundation to its community management features, every element was built with scalability, inclusiveness and ease-of-use in mind. WP2 successfully delivered the beta version (mock-up and first operational platform) in 2023, reaching milestone MS.3. Continuous updates were made in response to feedback from piloting (WP3), leading to this final version in August 2025 and milestone MS.6 – Final version of the platform available.

This report outlines the full journey and current state of the INDUSAC platform, detailing technical development, core functionalities, user engagement strategies, legal compliance, system performance, and its contribution to the overall INDUSAC mission and EU objectives.

II. Development Roadmap

The development of the INDUSAC platform (<https://indusac.innogetcloud.com/>), was carried out in a structured, phased approach to ensure technical robustness, alignment with the methodology and adaptability to user needs. WP2 defined key milestones, beginning with conceptual design and progressing through beta deployment, iterative updates and final delivery. This roadmap reflects the collaborative and human-centred principles that underpin the entire INDUSAC initiative.

2.1 Initial Requirements and Architecture

The foundation for the platform was established during the first project year through Tasks T2.1 and T2.2. INNOGET led efforts to define the **technical and legal framework**, ensuring compliance with EU regulations on data protection (GDPR), intellectual property and user rights.

Key outcomes from this phase included:

- **Technical Architecture (D2.1):** A modular and scalable system enabling matchmaking, collaboration, and project administration.
- **Legal Framework (D2.2):** Addressed privacy, liability, and ethical considerations, ensuring a secure environment for all users.
- **List of Technical Requirements (D2.3):** Mapped key platform functionalities and user expectations.

A human-centred approach guided the design process. This meant early alignment with the user journeys defined in WP1 and validation of functionality through user personas representing students, researchers and companies.

2.2 Beta Version and Pre-Validation

The first functional version of the INDUSAC platform (D2.4) was delivered in May 2023 as a **mock-up**, incorporating initial requirements into an interactive prototype. It underwent internal testing and was further refined before a controlled pre-validation session in August 2023 (D2.5).

Highlights from this stage:

- Testing with a controlled group of project partners and early users
- Validation of interface usability, task flows, and user onboarding
- Identification of early pain points (e.g., complex navigation, need for additional guidance material)
- Direct linkage with WP1 pre-validation workshop feedback

These insights fed into the development of the first public version of the platform, which officially launched in October 2023 (D2.6), marking the achievement of **Milestone MS.3**.

2.3 Full Launch and Iterative Improvement

Following the public release, WP2 prioritised user-driven development under **T2.5 – Continuous maintenance and update**. Updates were guided by data collected from WP3 piloting, community management efforts in T2.6, and Helpdesk support logs.

Key iterations included:

- Better **dashboard clarity** for companies and co-creation teams.
- Integration with **Slack**, enabling seamless communication and team assembly.
- Improved **support documentation**, including FAQs populated from real queries.

The platform supported **nine cut-off rounds** for student/researcher applications from February 2024 to April 2025, demonstrating its stability and adaptability across multiple usage waves.

Final improvements were implemented in mid-2025 and documented in this deliverable (D2.7), marking the achievement of **Milestone MS.6 – Final version of the platform available**.

III. Platform final features

3.1 User Registration and Onboarding

The platform offers a role-based registration system tailored for:

- **Companies**
- **Students**
- **Researchers**
- **University Representatives**

Figure 1: Registration & Log-in Page (<https://indusac.innogetcloud.com/#logincontent>)

Key Features:

- Email verification and GDPR-compliant consent collection
- Role-based dashboards (with contextual menus and prompts)
- Integrated guidance: tooltips, step-by-step onboarding, downloadable guides

User Experience Enhancements:

- Simplified forms and mobile-friendly design
- Dynamic user status indicators (e.g., “Challenge submitted”, “Application pending”)
- Platform orientation tooltips based on user type

3.2 Challenge Submission and Management (for Companies)

Companies access a dedicated Challenge Management Module allowing them to:

- Create and edit Challenges using structured templates
- Select Pre-defined Collaborative Approaches (PCAs) to fit their needs
- Set challenge timelines and evaluation criteria
- Review and approve incoming Motivation Letters
- Communicate directly with selected teams

Supportive Features:

- PCA selector tool based on sector, complexity, and duration
- Version history of submitted Challenges
- Notifications for application updates and upcoming deadlines

3.3 Matchmaking and Motivation Letter Workflow

Students and researchers can:

- Browse open Challenges
- Search/filter Challenges by country, sector, language, or timeline
- Join or create co-creation teams
- Submit a team Motivation Letter via a structured interface

Company users can:

- Review submissions in real time
- Approve or reject applicants with optional feedback
- Track team formation status and upcoming project start dates

Enhancements in Final Version:

- Team composition guidelines and validation checks (e.g., diversity by country)
- Motivation Letter templates and submission walkthrough
- Real-time Slack integration for co-creation team formation and discussion

3.4 Project Collaboration and Management

Once a team is approved, a **Project Workspace** is activated:

- Document sharing and version control
- Secure messaging and notification system

- Access to INDUSAC-provided guidance materials (user manuals, templates, FAQs)
- Project calendar with key dates and reminders

Monitoring Tools for INDUSAC Managers:

- View activity logs and project updates
- Track deliverables and completion dates
- Generate reports for internal evaluation

3.5 Support Features and Resources

- **Help Section:** FAQs, downloadable templates, platform tour
- **Slack Integration:** Real-time discussion, matchmaking, support
- **Feedback Channels:** Users can report bugs or submit suggestions
- **Language Support:** English interface with contextual support for multilingual needs

3.6 Analytics and Reporting

- Activity tracking dashboard for platform administrators
- KPIs: registrations, submitted Challenges, active teams, session durations
- Exportable CSV logs for evaluation purposes (linked to WP3 and WP5 needs)

IV. Platform Performance Metrics

The INDUSAC platform served as both a technical tool and a catalyst for building a pan-European community of industry-academia collaboration. Developed under WP2 and refined through piloting and stakeholder feedback, the platform not only supported challenge-based co-creation but also fostered inclusive, interdisciplinary, and geographically diverse engagement.

The effectiveness of the platform was assessed through a combination of **technical KPIs** and **community growth metrics**, aligning with Objectives 2 and 3 of the INDUSAC project.

4.1 Technical Performance

Table 1: Technical Performance Indicators

Indicator	Target	Final Result	Status
Platform uptime	≥ 99.9%	99.621%	Nearly achieved
Error tickets per 100 user sessions	≤ 1	1.3	Slight deviation
Requests for help per 10 user sessions	≤ 1	0.48 (525 /11,045)	Achieved
Avg time per visit	≥5 mins	6.6 mins	Achieved
Legal/privacy issues	0 unresolved cases	0	Achieved

These results demonstrate the platform's overall technical stability and legal robustness, with only minor deviations quickly addressed via real-time updates and support.

4.2 Community Engagement and Reach

The platform enabled active and meaningful participation across diverse stakeholder groups:

Table 2: Platform Usage Overview

Metric	Final Result
Registered users	1,400
- Students	~950
- Researchers	~180
- Companies	~270
Challenges published	251
Motivation letters received	232
Co-creation projects launched	164

Participants (platform users) represented **27 EU Member States and 16 EU associated countries**, with **67% from EU widening countries**, exceeding inclusiveness targets.

Additional highlights:

- Call for Students and Researchers with 9 cut-off dates facilitated through the platform
- Average time per session: **6 min 38 sec**
- Monthly logins (avg): **277**

This level of engagement supported both the **quantitative** and **qualitative** goals of INDUSAC: fostering rapid, diverse, and collaborative innovation across Europe.

V. Compliance and Legal Considerations

Legal compliance was a foundational pillar of the INDUSAC platform's design and operation. Ensuring the platform adhered to EU regulations – particularly those concerning data protection, privacy, intellectual property, and ethical standards – was essential to building user trust and safeguarding participants across all member states and associated countries.

All legal and regulatory measures were defined and implemented under **Task 2.1 (Platform Framework)** and documented in **Deliverable D2.2 – Legal Framework**. The final version of the platform fully complies with applicable European Union standards.

5.1 Data Protection (GDPR Compliance)

From the outset, the platform was designed in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), ensuring lawful, fair and transparent processing of all personal data.

Key compliance measures:

- Consent-based data collection and clear privacy notices
- Users could review and manage their personal data via their account settings
- Data access restricted to authorised personnel only
- Secure storage with encrypted communications (HTTPS protocol)
- Regular review of data handling practices in coordination with WP5 (Project Management)

No data breaches or unresolved data protection issues occurred during the project's lifetime.

5.2 Intellectual Property (IP) Rights

Given the nature of the co-creation process – involving original problem-solving between students, researchers and companies – IP protection was critical.

Platform safeguards and policies included:

- IP disclaimers and ownership clauses during registration and Challenge submission
- Visibility controls for Challenge content and submitted solutions
- Guidance provided to users regarding IP-sharing best practices

Where needed, companies were encouraged to request **non-disclosure agreements (NDAs)** prior to full disclosure of sensitive information. This helped balance transparency with IP security.

VI. Conclusion

The INDUSAC platform, developed under Work Package 2, has successfully delivered a robust, inclusive, and user-friendly digital environment that underpins the project's vision of quick, challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation between academia and industry.

Throughout the project lifetime, the platform evolved from a conceptual framework into a fully functional tool that facilitated transnational collaboration across 27 European Member States and 16 EU associated countries. It supported the publication of 251 company Challenges, enabled the formation of 164 co-creation teams, and served a registered community of over 1,400 users – including students, researchers, and industry professionals – with 67% participation from widening countries.

The platform's key achievements include:

- High user satisfaction and stability, with an uptime of 99.621% and strong ratings across usability and support dimensions
- Seamless integration of the INDUSAC methodology, with dedicated modules for onboarding and matchmaking.
- A scalable and legally compliant technical infrastructure, fully aligned with GDPR and EU ethical standards
- A vibrant, pan-European community built through digital engagement, Slack integration, and continuous improvement based on user feedback

By meeting its technical and strategic goals, the platform has directly contributed to the successful validation of the INDUSAC mechanism and has laid the groundwork for future replication and long-term sustainability.

Its modular design, legal foundation, and demonstrated impact make it a viable solution for integration into academic curricula, innovation clusters, and European co-creation initiatives beyond the lifespan of this project.

This final version of the platform, as documented in this deliverable, marks the achievement of Milestone MS.6: Final version of the platform available, and stands ready for further exploitation, scale-up, and integration into broader EU innovation ecosystems. The platform can be accessed at: <https://indusac.innogetcloud.com/>

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VIII. LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 Registration & Log-in Page

IX. LIST OF TABLES

Table 1	Technical Performance Indicators
Table 2	Platform Usage Overview

